

Development of Primary School Curriculum Among Asean Countries (Indonesia, Malaysia, Singapore, Thailand, Cambodia, Brunei Darusalam, and Laos)

Marsella Desriyarini Gui¹, Fatma Asneni², Rosita Inggile³, Reni R. Ahyani⁴, Dina Saripi⁵, Mutiara Pulumuduyo⁶, Ridwan G. Mootalu⁷, Melinda Maula⁸, Sri Meriyanti Daud⁹, Nurhayati Pakaya¹⁰

Faculty of Teacher Training and Education / Pohnuwo University

Corresponding Author: Marsella Desriyarini Gui Marsella1158@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Curriculum, Primary School, ASEAN

Received : 3 November

Revised : 18 November

Accepted: 20 December

©2023 Gui, Asneni, Inggile, Ahyani, Saripi, Pulumudoyo, Mootalu, Maula, Daud, Pakaya: This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Atribusi 4.0 Internasional](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

ABSTRACT

In both developed and developing countries, education is very important. Developed countries see education as a continuous effort to improve the quality of life of their people. Developing countries, on the other hand, need education to catch up with them in the international arena and be on par with developed countries. From this we know that the national curriculum is very important, it is even considered a measure of learning success. This is proven by the fact that the curriculum in Indonesia, Finland, Singapore, Malaysia, Cambodia, Thailand, Brunei Darussalam, the Philippines, Laos, and so on. This research explores various literature related to curriculum from various countries. The national education curriculum was changed several times after independence. This happened in 1947, 1952, 1964, 1968, 1975, 1984, 1994, 2004, 2006, 2013, and 2020, 2022. In curriculum changes, we can find the best curriculum. The Indonesian education curriculum must emphasize the development of Indonesian human character who has faith and devotion to God Almighty. The curriculum is different in Indonesia and several other countries, but these differences are made to improve education in these countries

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important elements in life is education. Since this interaction with educational activities, humans have made various developments and advances in various fields. At the same time, the educational process is progressing very rapidly in terms of methods and objectives (Educational curriculum and assessment standards agency, 2022). This is one of the characteristics of education that continues to develop. Education cannot be considered something if it does not produce progress or even causes regression. Education is basically an important activity that includes goals, methods and means to develop individuals who are able to communicate and adapt to their environment. The Indonesian government must make changes in the education sector to improve the quality of education. The curriculum is the only way to improve the quality of education. To advance a nation, including Indonesia, where laws and other regulations guarantee education, the basis, model and principles for developing an educational curriculum are very important. Moreover, in the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution there is a state ideal, namely to make the nation's life intelligent, which means that education is the key to making this happen.

The government uses the curriculum as a basis for improving the quality of education (Kemendikbudristek, 2022). When students have a comfortable learning experience, they can understand well what their educators or teachers say. Curriculum planning and development by the government, schools, or related parties to achieve national education goals is known as curriculum development. The curriculum has a strategic role in education, so it should not be prepared and developed arbitrarily.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Religious, moral, political, social and cultural values can be used to build student character (Hasan, 2008). Additional factors must also be considered, such as student needs, current developments, and teacher or educational capabilities. Goals based on philosophical principles are the main component of curriculum creation (Mulyada, 2021). In this way, the author attempts to examine and describe the evolution of the curriculum in elementary schools in Indonesia and various other countries. The government often used the curriculum as a political tool during the pre-independence period. For example, when the Netherlands and Japan colonized Indonesia, the curriculum had to be adjusted to the political interests of the two countries. The school curriculum is based on the noble values of the nation as a representation of Indonesian society after Indonesia gained independence in 1945.

The national school curriculum was changed several times after independence. This happened in 1947, 1952, 1964, 1968, 1975, 1984, 1994, 2004, 2006, and 2013 (Insani, 2019:46). Furthermore, the curriculum was changed in 2020 and 2022. This change is a logical consequence of the socio-political, cultural, economic, and scientific and technological structures in social, national and state life in 2022. The curriculum has been changed thirteen times over 70 years. Indonesian independence.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses a literature review research method. This research requires data from libraries, documents or scientific journals. The goal is to gain an understanding of previous research. Data collected, analyzed and concluded as part of a literature study. Secondary data is data that is not collected through direct observation, processed, and used as support by other parties involved in this research. This data will be used in this research. Previous studies, such as books, scientific reports, journals, and news about traditional games, provide data sources for data collection methods. We as researchers function as the main tool for finding data and information in this research. Data reduction, data delivery, and drawing conclusions or verification are three processes that occur simultaneously in data analysis (Burhan Bungin, 2008).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The curriculum is the core of education, consisting of three main areas: curriculum, student guidance, and educational management. The curriculum has the greatest direct influence on student development. The term "curriculum" comes from the Latin "curriculae", which means the distance a runner must cover. At that time, the curriculum was the educational time a student spent to earn a diploma. In other words, the curriculum is considered a very important means to achieve the goals of a journey. The curriculum is recognized by obtaining a certain diploma.

Indonesian Education

The government often used the curriculum as a political tool before independence. For example, the curriculum must be adapted to the political interests of the Netherlands and Japan during the Indonesian colonial period. The school curriculum was adapted to political interests after Indonesia became an independent country in 1945. This curriculum is based on national values as a representation of Indonesian society. These changes are the logical result of the 2022 socio-political, cultural, economic and technological systems in the lives of society, nation and state. The curriculum has been changed thirteen times during the 70 years of Indonesian independence.

In detail, during the Old Order (Orla), or when President Soekarno was in power, the curriculum changed three times. These are the 1947 Lesson Plan Curriculum, the 1964 Elementary School Education Plan Curriculum, and the 1968 Elementary School Curriculum. The curriculum changed six times during the New Order (Orba), or the government of President Soeharto. These include the 1973 School Development Pilot Project Curriculum, the 1975 Elementary School Curriculum, the 1975 Curriculum, the 1984 Curriculum, the 1994 Curriculum, and the 1997 Curriculum Review Curriculum. The curriculum has changed three times since the end of the New Order or the beginning of the reforms. This includes the 2004 Competency-Based Curriculum (KBK), the 2006 Learning Unit Level Curriculum (KTSP), and the 2013 Curriculum (Hamalik Oemar. 2008).

Indonesian Curriculum History Concept Map

The chart below shows a concept map regarding the history of curriculum development in Indonesia after independence

Sumber: Materi Persentasi Kemendikbud 2015
 Picture 1. Curriculum Development Concept Map

Then, twenty years after the 1998 reform, precisely during the COVID-19 pandemic, the Ministry of Education and Culture changed the 2013 curriculum to the 2022–2024 prototype curriculum. This is a way to respond to various changes caused by the COVID-19 pandemic and adapt to the Industrial Revolution 4.0.

Table 1. Chronology of the Development of Education Programs in Indonesia

Year	Curriculum	Description
1947	Lesson Plan (Lesson Plan Details Unraveled) 1947	This curriculum was the first curriculum in Indonesia after independence, and the term "curriculum" was still not used. Instead, the term used is RPP.
1964	Plan (Primary Education) 1964	The exchange rate offered remains the same as previously offered.
1968	1968 Elementary School Curriculum	1968 Elementary School Curriculum: The first integrated curriculum in Indonesia. Social Sciences (IPS) is a term used to combine several scientific disciplines, such as history, earth sciences, and several branches of social sciences. Natural Sciences (IPA), or what is now often called "Natural Sciences", is a new name for several scientific disciplines, such as Life Sciences and Natural Sciences.

1973	1973 Curriculum (PPSP)	Printed School Curriculum Development Program 1973 (PPSP) in 1973
1975	1975 Elementary School Curriculum	These rates are arranged in very detailed columns.
1984	1984 Curriculum	1984 Curriculum The 1984 curriculum was improved from the 1975 curriculum.
1994	1994 Curriculum	This exchange rate is an improvement from the one that existed in 1984.
1997	1997 Curriculum (1994 Curriculum Revision)	1994 Revised Curriculum
2004	(Pioneering Competency Based Curriculum (KBK)	This curriculum has not been implemented in all schools in Indonesia. Several schools were used as trials in the process of creating this curriculum.
2006	Education Unit Level Curriculum (KTSP)	The KBK curriculum, which was developed by the BSNP (National Education Standards Agency), actually adopted the KTSP. Because of this, KBK is often referred to as the soul of KTSP.
2013	2013 Curriculum	The focus of the curriculum is competency-based thinking skills, skills and knowledge that can build productive, creative, innovative and affective Indonesian individuals by improving integrated attitudes, skills and knowledge.
2020	Emergency Curriculum Prototype Curriculum	The Ministry of Education and Culture issued an emergency curriculum policy to overcome the COVID-19 pandemic. The simplified 2013 curriculum is used as this emergency curriculum. After the emergency curriculum was implemented, the government created a prototype curriculum that focused on soft skills and characters such as faith, piety, noble morals, mutual cooperation, global diversity, independence, critical reasoning and creativity. Focus on important topics such as numeracy and literacy. Accessibility of teachers to deliver learning according to student abilities, local context, and content.
2022	Independent 2022 Curriculum	In 2022, three curriculum options have been provided for teachers and schools to use. Uses all of the 2013 curriculum, including the emergency curriculum, which simplifies the independent curriculum. As a result, an independent curriculum is just one option. Schools and educators can also choose between the two options. They are given the freedom to choose a curriculum that suits their respective school circumstances.

Education in Malaysia

The best curriculum emphasizes moral, intelligence, emotional, skill and physical development (Alimin, 2004). Learning objectives also emphasize understanding concepts and problem solving abilities. Preschool, primary, and secondary education in Malaysia is under the supervision of the Malaysian Ministry of Education (KPM). Formal education starts from preschool, lower education, secondary education, pre-university education, and higher education. As of 2004, the country's formal education system is overseen by the Ministry of Education. Meanwhile, the Ministry of Higher Education (Ministry of Higher Education) is responsible for higher education (Creswell, John. W. 2009). Basically, schools in Malaysia and Indonesia are not much different. The Malaysian government is trying to make its country a center for quality education and ready to compete with higher education institutions in other countries such as Singapore and Australia. Education in the two countries differs in the names of the levels. Education levels also differ. For example, secondary school in Malaysia starts in 5 years, while in Indonesia it takes 6 years. Education in Malaysia is more advanced because the curriculum is fixed and does not change frequently, in contrast to Indonesia, where policies and curricula change frequently, so that technical implementation is slow to develop (Amelia, 2012).

Education in Singapore

Singapore's human and educational resources are very good, especially in Southeast Asia. As a result, Singapore has become one of the most preferred countries to study. Singapore's education system has evolved from the traditional British model to one aimed at meeting individual needs and developing students' talents. Singapore's education system is excellent because it has a dual language policy (English and a mother tongue, such as Malay, Mandarin, or Tamil in Thailand) and a comprehensive curriculum that prioritizes innovation and entrepreneurship. Individuals show talents that are related to each other and the ability to survive in an environment full of competition and are prepared for a brighter future (Elisa, S & Wrastari, A. 2013).

Formal education in Singapore starts from Kindergarten (TK) or the equivalent in Indonesia. Students continue to elementary school (SD) level for six years after graduating. Students must remain in high school for four or five years to advance to higher levels. Students learn English, Mother Tongue, Mathematics, Science, and (Social) Culture in this pathway. Schools are permitted to offer applied subjects (AGS) in addition to or in place of the curriculum to give students a variety of choices. AGS usually encourages students to practice or oriented education such as polytechnics. Many factors support Singapore's progress. Having adequate facilities is one of them. For example, every school in Singapore has free internet access and has a school website that helps connect parents, students and teachers. One of the additional benefits it offers is an accessible transportation system in every school in Singapore, which makes it easier for students to go to school (Sri Wiryawan, A and Noorhadi. 2001).

In Singapore, education costs are adjusted to suit each person's abilities, and they also provide scholarships to less fortunate students. The educational factor also makes Singapore the country with the best education system in

ASEAN. The teacher appointment process is very strict, and the teacher candidates accepted are adjusted to the number of teachers required. Thus, every prospective teacher will definitely be hired. Prospective teachers are given pre-employment training after they are selected. This ensures that teachers have acquired knowledge before they work. Apart from that, the large salaries for teachers in Singapore guarantee their welfare.

Thai Education

Thailand, a country with a population of nearly 70 million people, has an education system that is very similar to Indonesia's education system, with slight differences ranging from early childhood education to tertiary education. Vocational education in Indonesia has a length of study of 3 (three) years, equivalent to a Diploma 2, while in Thailand it is 5 (five) years (Chantra Tantipongsanuruk. 2013).

Therefore, polytechnic colleges are not as well known in Thailand as they are in Indonesia. Thai Polytechnics are "longlife learning" institutions that provide certificates for specific skills. Like Indonesia, Thailand also implements 9 years of compulsory education. However, they provide free education until high school graduation. The success of Thai education has always depended on science and technology, so everything produced is based on research and research. Every activity must generate profits in addition to supporting other education by maintaining cultural values so that Thailand becomes a clean, orderly and disciplined country and still adheres to the ideology that exists and is developing in that country. In Thailand, teachers concentrate on one full assignment. Teachers called "Kunkru" are the determinants of educational success, not so different from in Indonesia (Office of Education Council. 2013).

Cambodian Education

From at least the 13th century, an educational system existed. Traditionally, Cambodian education was given only to men and was provided in Wats (Buddhist monasteries). Education includes basic religion, language, and everyday skills. "Traditional" education gradually changed when French colonists entered Cambodia. They introduced a formal education system influenced by the Western education model, with a 6+3+3 structure meaning 12 years to complete general education. Two other parts of Cambodia's educational structure are non-formal education, which is available to all children, youth, adults, people with disabilities, and provides access to life skills. An additional factor is teacher training. The Cambodian state currently manages the education system, but the private sector now manages private education at all levels. Most private schools provide general education and are owned by ethnic and religious minority communities. Private universities are available in all provinces of Cambodia, but especially in the country's capital. The National Curriculum for schools in Cambodia consists of two main parts: primary education and senior secondary school (Majid, 2010).

Brunei Darussalam Education

The curriculum in Indonesia and Brunei Darussalam is not much different. However, the concept of Malay Islamic Beraja (MIB) is taught in Brunei Darussalam schools. The main goal is to create human resources who are moral, religious and technologically adept. Apart from that, the education system is very similar to the system in "commonwealth" countries such as England, Malaysia, Singapore, and others. In contrast to Indonesia, Brunei has implemented a new education system called SPN21 (21st Century State Education System). This system is intended to provide students with the opportunity and flexibility to achieve a higher educational status according to their academic abilities, enabling them to develop their talents (Kusneidi and Surya, 2010).

The school curriculum in Brunei Darussalam focuses on subjects. Starting from preschool to middle school, there are 7 to 9 subjects taught at each level of education, and there are 12 subjects taught before high school. In the process of developing the vocational school curriculum, learning materials have referred to occupational competency standards that are in accordance with the needs of industry or the business world. An interesting thing is that English has been taught from kindergarten to lower elementary school, namely from first to third grade. On the other hand, bilingual language use (bilingualism) begins in upper elementary school, grades four to six, and high school. However, some subjects must be taught in Malay, such as Islamic religious education, arts and crafts, and Malay Islam Berjaya (MIB) (Ratna, 2014). However, subjects such as mathematics, history, science and geography must be taught in English. Starting from preschool to middle school, there are 7 to 9 subjects taught at each level of education, and there are 12 subjects taught before high school. In the process of developing the vocational school curriculum, learning materials have referred to job competency standards that are in accordance with the needs of industry or the business world (Suprayekti, 2007).

Lao Education

Laos became the language of instruction at all levels of education after the 1975 revolution succeeded. Education in Laos currently consists of five years of primary (compulsory) education, three years of lower secondary education, three years of upper secondary education, and three to seven years of post-school education, depending on the field of study. However, at the age of six, children can attend school. The use of modern technology in Lao education is very limited, and the national curriculum is very standard (Sujiono, N. Yuliani. 2012).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The government and related parties can assess the quality of a country's education. Curriculum development, which aims to create a comfortable learning environment, can be used to determine the quality of education. A person's curriculum can influence their educational progress. So, studying curriculum development is a way to find out many things about the education system, especially those related to the advantages and disadvantages of the system. The national school curriculum was changed in 1947, 1952, 1964, 1968, 1975, 1984, 1994, 2004, 2006, 2013, and 2020, 2022 after independence. The changed

curriculum in Indonesia and in several other countries is different, but these differences are an effort to improve the quality of education in each country. The best curriculum in Indonesia must emphasize the formation of a complete Indonesian human character who has faith and devotion to God Almighty

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic Development of Primary School Curriculum Among Countries in order to improve this research and add insight to readers.

REFERENCES

- Alimin, Z. (2004). Reorientasi Konsep Pendidikan Khusus Pendidikan Kebutuhan Khusus dan Implikasinya Terhadap Layanan Pendidikan. *Jurnal Asesmen dan Intervensi Anak Berkebutuhan Khusus* 3(1), 52-63.
- Amelia, L. (2012). Pengembangan Modul Peningkatan Guru Dalam Pembelajaran di Sekolah Dasar Inklusif. *Jurnal Pendidikan Inlusif*. PKK SPs UPI. Bandung.
- Badan Standar Kurikulum dan Asesmen Pendidikan. (2022). *Kajian Akademik Kurikulum untuk Pemulihan Pembelajaran (1st ed.)*. Kementerian Pendidikan Kebudayaan Riset dan Teknologi. [https://ditpsd.kemdikbud.go.id/upload/filemanager/download/kurikulummerdeka/Kajian Akademik Kurikulum untuk Pemulihan Pembelajaran \(2\).pdf](https://ditpsd.kemdikbud.go.id/upload/filemanager/download/kurikulummerdeka/Kajian_Akademik_Kurikulum_untuk_Pemulihan_Pembelajaran_(2).pdf)
- Burhan Bungin. 2008. *Penelitian Kualitatif*. Jakarta ; Prenada Media Group
- Chantra Tantipongsanuruk (2013), "Personal Communication"
- Creswell, John. W. (2009). *Research Design Qualitative Quantitative and mixed methods approaches*.
- Direktorat Sekolah Dasar. (2022). *Buku Saku Serba-Serbi Kurikulum Merdeka Kekhasan Sekolah Dasar*. Direktur Sekolah Dasar, Kemendikbudristek.
- Elisa, S & Wrastari, A. (2013). Sikap Guru Terhadap Pendidikan Inklusi Ditinjau Dari Faktor Pemebntukan Sikap. *Jurnal Psikologi Perkembangan dan Pendidikan* 2(1), 1-10.
- Hamalik Oemar. 2008. *Dasar-dasar Pengembangan Kurikulum*. Bandung ; Remaja Rosdakarya
- Hasan, S.H. 2008. *Evaluasi Kurikulum*. Bandung ; Rosdakarya

- Kusnendi & Suryadi. (2010). Kearifan Lokal dan Perilaku Edukatif, Ilmiah, Religius. Proceeding of The 4th International Conference on Teacher Education; Join conference UPI& UPSI Bandung, Indonesia. 8-10 November 2010.
- Majid. (2010). Perencanaan Pembelajaran: Mengembangkan Standar Kompetensi Guru. Bandung: Remaja Rosda Karya.
- Maullyda, M. A., Erfan, M., & Hidayati, V. R. (2021). Analisis Situasi Pembelajaran Selama Pandemi Covid-19 di SDN Senurus: Kemungkinan Terjadinya Learning Loss. *Collase (Creative of Learning Students Elementary Education)*, 04(03), 328-336.
<https://journal.ikipsiliwangi.ac.id/index.php/collase/article/viewFile/7140/2397>
- Office of Education Council (2013), "Curriculum Development of Thai Basic Education", Ministry of Education, Bangkok, Thailand
- Ratna. (2014). Program Parenting Dalam Pengasuhan Anak Berbasis Karakter. Tesis pada Program Manajemen Pendidikan UNINUS Bandung: Tidak diterbitkan
- Sri Wiryawan, A dan Noorhadi. (2001). Strategi Belajar Mengajar. Jakarta: Pusat Penerbitan Universitas Terbuka.
- Sujiono, N.Yuliani. (2012). Konsep Dasar Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini. Jakarta: Penerbit PT Indeks.
- Suprayekti. (2007), Pembaharuan Pembelajaran di SD. Jakarta: Universitas Terbuka